

Histomorphology and Immunohistochemistry in Diagnosing Soft Tissue Tumors

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Abstract

Background: Soft tissue tumors are uncommon and comprise about 2% or less of surgical pathology cases. The annual incidence of soft tissue tumor is 1.4 per 100000 population [3]. Soft tissue tumors are the fourth most common malignancy in children, after neoplasms, neural tumors, and Wilms tumor. Benign tumors outnumber malignant ones by margin of 100:1 [4]. Many soft tissue neoplasms, however, show spindle cell, epithelioid cell, small round cell or pleomorphic morphology on initial examination and require further characterization by immunohistochemistry.

Methodology: This study was conducted in the Department of Pathology at Sher-i- Kashmir Institute of Medical Sciences (SKIMS), Srinagar. It was a prospective study of 1 ½ years from November 2017 to April 2019.

Complete clinical details, examination findings, and radiological investigations of all patients were studied. The excised tissue specimens were processed routinely, stained with Hematoxylin and Eosin and examined, while special stains like Immunohistochemistry were performed as required. Diagnostic results from patients were compared for diagnostic concordance using immunohistochemistry results as the gold standard where ever required.

Results: There were 101(67.33%) benign tumors and 36(24%) malignant tumors and 13 were (8.66%) intermediate tumors with a benign- malignant ratio of 2.80:1. Of total number of cases 88 were males and 62 were females with male to female ratio of 1.38:1 and mean age of 39.38. Male to female ratio among benign tumors was 1.33:1 ,among intermediate group was 1.14:1 and among malignant tumors 2:1. Benign tumors were more common on extremities 47 cases (47%) and head and neck 34 cases(33.66%). Intermediate group tumors were mostly commonly found in trunk and retroperitoneum 9 cases(69%). Malignant tumors were common on lower extremities 18 cases(50%) followed by retroperitoneum 8 cases(22.2%). Adipocytic tumors were the most common category found with 41 cases(27.33%) followed by Vascular tumors 31 cases(20.66%) and Peripheral nerve sheath tumors 28 cases(18.66%).

Conclusion: Our study highlights the importance of affected age group, sexual predilection, location, size, histopathology, and IHC features in diagnosing STTs.

Limitation: Tumors of uncertain differentiation were even difficult to categorize using IHC. Hence, cytogenetic and molecular studies may be needed to accurately diagnose these tumors.

Keywords: STTs, IHC.

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Introduction

Soft tissue tumors are uncommon and comprise about 2% or less of surgical pathology cases [1,2]. The annual incidence of soft tissue tumor is 1.4 per 100000 population [3]. Soft tissue tumors are the fourth most common malignancy in children, after neoplasms, neural tumors, and Wilms tumor. Benign tumors outnumber malignant ones by margin of 100:1 [4] Many soft tissue neoplasms, however, show spindle cell, epithelioid cell, small round cell or pleomorphic morphology on initial examination and require further characterization by immunohistochemistry.

Sarcoma Grading

Several different grading systems have been developed. The two most widely used are the U.S. National Cancer Institute (NCI) and the French Fédération Nationale des Centres de Lutte Contre le Cancer (FNCLCC) systems, both of which assign sarcomas into three tiers and have demonstrated prognostic value.[5-7]

The FNCLCC grading system requires evaluation of three parameters: tumor differentiation, mitotic count, and tumor necrosis (Table below).[8,9]

FRENCH (FNCLCC) Grading System

1. Tumor Differentiation

Score 1- Sarcomas that closely resemble normal adult mesenchymal tissues

Score 2- Sarcomas for which histologic typing is certain

Score 3-Embryonal and undifferentiated sarcomas, synovial sarcoma, and sarcomas of uncertain differentiation

2. Mitotic Count

Score 1- 0–9 mitoses/10 hpf

Score 2- 10–19 mitoses/10 hpf Score 3 ≥ 20 mitoses/10 hpf

3. Tumor Necrosis Score 0 No necrosis

Score 1- <50% tumor necrosis

Score 2- $\geq 50\%$ tumor necrosis

Histologic Grade (tumor differentiation + mitotic count + tumor necrosis)

Grade 1 (low grade) Total score: 2 or 3

Grade 2 (intermediate grade) Total score: 4 or 5

Grade 3 (high grade) Total score: 6, 7, or 8

Aims and Objectives

The aims and objectives of the study are as under:

1. To study the histopathological spectrum of soft tissue tumors in relation to age, gender and anatomical site.
2. To study histopathology of both benign and malignant soft tissue tumors.
3. Confirmation of the diagnosis by

immunohistochemistry wherever needed.

Materials and Methods

This study was be conducted in the Department of Pathology at Sher-i-Kashmir Institute of Medical Sciences (SKIMS), Srinagar. It was a prospective study of 1 ½ years from November 2017 to April 2019.

Complete clinical details, examination

findings, and radiological investigations of all patients were studied. The excised tissue specimens were processed routinely, stained with Hematoxylin and Eosin and examined, while special stains like Immunohistochemistry were performed as required. Diagnostic results from patients were compared for diagnostic concordance using immunohistochemistry results as the gold standard where ever required.

Inclusion Criteria:

Observations and Results

Both benign and malignant soft tissue tumors were included in the study and classified according to WHO classification.

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Tumors arising from bone infiltrating into soft tissue were excluded.
2. Metastatic lesions were not included in the study.
3. Uterine and visceral soft tissue tumors were not included in the study.

Table 1: Distribution of cases in males and females

SEX	Benign	%	Inter- mediate	%	Malignant	%	Total	%
Male	58	40%	7	5.33%	23	13.33%	88	58.66%
Female	43	30%	6	4.66%	13	6.66%	62	41.33%
Total	101	70%	13	10%	36	20%	150	100%

$\chi^2:0.5936$

1. Of 150 cases there were 101 benign tumors (70%) 13(10%) were in the intermediate group and 36(20%) were malignant tumors.
2. Among males there were 58 cases (40%) of benign tumors,23 Cases (13.33%) of malignant tumors and 7 cases (5.33%) of intermediate group tumors.
3. Among females there are 43 cases (30%) of benign tumors,13 Cases (6.66%) of malignant tumors and 6 cases (4.66%) of intermediate group tumors.

Figure 1: Showing the distribution of tumors according to their nature (Benign, intermediate, or malignant)

Sex Wise Distribution of Cases

Figure 2: Showing sex wise distribution of cases

Table 2: Age wise distribution of cases

	Benign	Intermediate	Malignant	Total
	N=101 (67.33%)	N=13 (8.66%)	N=36 (24%)	N=150 (100%)
Upto 10 years	2		3	5(3.33%)
11-20 years	5		3	8(5.33%)
21-30 years	32	3	2	37(24.66%)
31-40 years	36	2	5	43(28.66%)
41-50years	11	5	4	24(16%)
51-60years	7	1	8	16(10.66%)
61-70years	4	1	8	13(8.66%)
>70YEARS		1	3	4(2.66%)

X²:0.493

- In our study maximum number of cases were seen in the age group of 31-40 years with 43 cases (28.66%) followed by age group of 21-30 years with 37 cases (24%), 41-50 years with 24 cases (16%), 51-60 years with 16 cases (10.66%).
- Least number of cases were seen in the age group of 10 years with 5 cases (3.33%)

Table 3: Showing histopathological typing of soft tissue tumors.

Tumor Differentiation	Benign	Intermediate	Malignant	Total
Adipocytic tumors	31(30.69%)	2(15.38%)	8(22.22%)	41(27.33%)
Vascular	27(26.73%)	2(15.38%)	2(5.55%)	31(20.66%)
Pericytic tumors	2(1.98%)			2(1.33%)
Peripheral nerve sheath tumors	26(25.74.%)		2(5.55%)	28(18.66%)
Fibroblastic	4(3.96%)	6(46.15%)	2(5.55%)	12(8%)
Fibrohistocytic	6(5.94%)	3(23.07%)	2(5.55%)	11(7.33%)
Smooth muscle tumors	4(3.96%)		6(16.66%)	10(8%)
Skeletal muscle tumors	1(0.99%)		7(19.44%)	8(5.33%)
Synovial Sarcoma			5(13.88%)	5(2.66%)
PNET/extra skeletal Ewings sarcoma			2(5.55%)	2(1.33%)
Total	101(100%)	13(100%)	36(100%)	150(100%)

- Adipocytic tumors were the most common category found with 41 cases (27.33%) followed by Vascular tumors 31 cases (20.66%) and Peripheral nerve sheath tumors 28 cases (18.66%).
- Fibroblastic tumors and fibrohistocytic tumors constituted 12 cases (8%) and 11(7.33%) of total cases respectively.
- There were 10 cases (8%) of smooth muscle tumors,8 cases of skeletal muscle tumors (5.33%).
- Among tumors of uncertain differentiation were 5 cases (2.66%) of synovial sarcoma and 2 cases (1.33%) of PNET/extra skeletal wings
- Lipoma formed the bulk of benign adipocytic tumors constituting 31(30.69%) of cases.
- Most common malignant soft tissue tumor was liposarcoma with 8 cases (22.22%)
- Fibroblastic tumors were the most common group in the intermediate category with 6 cases (46.15%).

Table 4: Showing distribution of intermediate and malignant tumors according to site

S No.	Sarcoma	Head And Neck	Extre Mities		Trunk	Retro-Perito Neum	Total
			Upper	Lower			
1	Liposarcoma			3		5	8
2	Leiomyosarcoma			3	1	2	6
3	Rhabdomyosarcoma	4		2	1		7
4	Myxofibrosarcoma		1	1			2
5	Fibrohistocytic (Undifferentiated pleomorphic sarcoma)			2			2
6	MPNST			1		1	2
7	Angiosarcoma		1	1			2
8	Atypical Lipomatous tumor/ well diff liposarcoma			1		1	2
9	Fibromatosis				1	1	2
10	IMT				1	1	2
11	Malignant SFT				1	1	2
12	DFSP		1		2		3
13	Hemangioendothelioma			2			2
14	Synovial sarcoma	1		4			5
15	Extra skeletal Ewings/PNET			1	1		2
	Total	6	3	20	8	12	49

Table 5 : Showing FNLCC grading of malignant soft tissue sarcoma

Sarcoma	FNLCC GRADE I	FNLCC II	FNLCC III	TOTAL
Liposarcoma	3	2	1	6
Leiomyosarcoma	1	3	2	6
Rhabdomyosarcoma	4	3		7
Myxofibrosarcoma		1		1
MPNST		2		2
Malignant Hemangioendothelioma		3		3
Angiosarcoma		3	1	4

Synovial sarcoma		4		4
Extra skeletal Ewings/PNET			1	1
Pleomorphic sarcoma		1	1	2
Total	8	22	6	36

- Majority of soft tissue sarcomas were grade-II – 22 cases.
- P-value:0.021

Table 6: Showing distribution of benign tumors according to site

Tumor Type	Head And Neck	Extre- Mities		Trunk	Retropo- Ritoneum	Total
		upper	lower			
Lipoma	13	9	2	7		31
Hemangioma	17	7	1	2(2%)		27
Glomus tumor		2				2
Neural	2	8	10	5(2.66%)	1(0.66%)	26
Elastofibroma, Angiofibroma		1	1	2(0.66%)		4
Giant cell tumor of tendon sheath		2				
Benign fibrous histiocytoma	1		2	1		6
Leiomyoma		2		2		4
Rhabdomyoma	1					1
Total	34	31	16	19	1(0.66%)	101

In present study 45.54% benign soft tissue tumors were seen in extremities followed by head and neck 32.23, p-value:0.001.

The malignant soft tissue tumors were observed to have a strong Predilection for extremities 57.14% specifically lower extremities, followed by trunk and abdomen 22.85%.

Table 7: Showing immunohistochemistry of malignant soft tissue tumors

Tumors	Markers showing positivity	No of positive cases (%)	Total no of cases
Liposarcoma	CD34	4(66.66%)	6
	S 100	3(50%)	
Leiomyosarcoma	SMA, Desmin,	6(100%)	6
	H caldesmon	5(83.33%)	
Rhabdomyosarcoma	Desmin,, vimentin	7(100%)	7
	Myogenin,	7(100%)	
Myxofibrosarcoma	CD99, vimentin, CD34,	2(100%)	2
MPNST	S100 focal positivity	1(50%)	2
Malignant Hemangioendothelioma	CD 34	1(50%)	2
Angiosarcoma	CD31, FLI1, CD34	2(100%)	2
	Cd31, FLI1+	2(100%)	

Synovial sarcoma	Ck7+, Vimentin	4(80%)	5
	CD99	3(60%)	
Extra skeletal Ewing's/PNET	CD99, Vimentin	2(100%)	2
	CK, FLI1	1(50%)	
Pleomorphic sarcoma	Focal SMA positivity	1(50%)	2

- IHC was done in 36 malignant tumors, 13 intermediate category tumors, and 10 benign cases. The IHC positivity in different tumor groups is shown in Table 11. A definitive diagnosis was reached in 33/36 malignant, 7/13 intermediate, and 9/10 benign tumors.

Figure 3: Gross photograph of a fibrosarcoma with a well encapsulated surface and greyish to tan cut section.

Figure 4: Gross photograph of a lipoma with well encapsulated external surface and a yellow, homogenous cut section

Figure 5: Gross photograph of a cutaneous leiomyosarcoma ulcerating through skin.

Figure 6: Gross photograph of a pleomorphic sarcoma with a variegated cut section

Figure 7: Photomicrograph of a well differentiated liposarcoma- sclerosing variant (10X,H and E)

Figure 8: Photomicrograph of a well differentiated liposarcoma -sclerosing variant showing atypical stromal cells (40x,H and E)

Figure 9: Photomicrograph of dermatofibro sarcoma protruberans showing CD34 positivity (40x,DAB Chromogen)

Figure 10: Photomicrograph of a pleomorphic undifferentiated sarcoma showing focal smooth muscle actin positivity (40X, DAB Chromogen)

Discussion

This study was carried out in the Department of Pathology, Sher-I-Kashmir Institute of Medical Sciences, Srinagar over a period of one and half years from November 2017 to April 2019. A total of 13933 surgical specimens were received in the department during the study period of which soft tissue tumor constituted 150 (1.07%) cases.

Sex Incidence

Of total number of cases 88 were males and 62 were females with male to female ratio of 1.38:1 and mean age of 39.38. Male to female ratio among benign tumors was 1.33:1, among intermediate group was 1.14:1 and among malignant tumors 2:1

Mirza Asif [10] in his study found an overall male to female ratio for benign soft tissue tumors 1.13:1 and for malignant soft tissue tumors 1:1 while Kransdorf *et al* [11,12] found male to female ratio for benign tumors as 1.3:1 and for malignant tumors as 1.2:1.

Enzinger and Weiss (2001) [4] reported a benign to malignant ratio of 100:1.

This analyzes the fact that benign soft tissue tumors outnumber their malignant counterparts. Soft tissue sarcoma is extremely rare and accounts for less than 1% of all cancers [4]. In the present study soft tissue sarcomas accounted for 1.07% of all tumors. In the present study ratio of benign-malignant

tumors is 1.38:1 but Enzinger and Weiss (2001) mentions benign-malignant ratio of 100:1. This is due to the fact that many benign tumors such as lipoma and hemangioma do not undergo biopsy as compared to sarcoma, which come to medical attention quite early.

Age wise distribution

In our study maximum number of cases were seen in the age group of 31-40 years with 43 cases (24.66%) followed by 21-30 years with 37 cases (24.66%), 41-50 years with 24 cases (16%), 51-60 years with 16 cases (10.66%). The study of Jobanputra *et al* [13] yielded similar results. Age of cases in our study were ranging from 0 to 70 years. Peak incidence of the tumors were in the age group of 31 to 40 years (43 cases, 24.66%), followed by 21 to 30 years (37 cases, 24.66%).

Incidence of tumors were found decreased in both the extreme of age group which are in the 0 to 10 years (5 cases, 3.33%) and > 70 years (4 cases, 2.66%). Highest number of malignant tumors were found in the 51 to 70 (16 cases, 19%) years of age group. It shows chances of malignancy are more in advancing age group. Study of Jobanputra *et al* [13] yielded similar results.

Distribution of cases in males and females: Of 150 cases there were 101 benign tumors (70%). 13 (10%) were in the intermediate group and 36 (20%) were

malignant tumors. Among males there were 58 cases (40%) of benign tumors, 23 Cases (13.33%) of malignant tumors and 7 cases (5.33%) of intermediate group tumors.

Among females there were 43 cases (30%) of benign tumors, 13 Cases (6.66%) of malignant tumors and 6 cases (4.66%) of

intermediate group tumors. Study of Navya Narayanan [14] had 93.8% as benign tumors, 3.4% intermediate group tumors and 2.8% as malignant group tumors. Petersen *et al* [15] did a retrospective study and found 49% malignant, 11.4% intermediate, 35% benign and 4.6% as tumors of uncertain potential.

Table 8: Showing Comparative analysis of age, sex and anatomical site distribution of soft tissue tumors

	Geeta Dev <i>et al</i> [16,17] (1974)		Kransdorf <i>et al</i> [11,12] (1995)		Mirza Asif B [10] (2013)		Present study (2019)	
	Benign	Malignant	Benign	Malignant	Benign	Malignant	Benign	Malignant
Incidence (%)	83.8	16.4	60.2	39.8	82.48	17.52	67.33%	24%
Ratio (benign malignant)	5.2:1		1.5:1		4.70:1		2.80:1	
Average age	29.6	36.0	34.6	40.4	29.2	37.8	39.38	
M:F	1.7:1	2.4:1	1.3:1	1.2:1	1.13:1	1:1	1.38:1	2:1
Anatomical common site	Head and neck	Lower extremity	Upper extremity	Lower extremity	Head, neck and trunk	Lower extremity	Lower extremity	Lower extremity

In the present study, there were 101(67.33%) benign tumors and 36(24%) malignant group tumors and 13 were (8.66%) (Table 2) intermediate tumors with a benign-malignant ratio of 2.80:1. Our study is at variance with study of Jain *et al* [18] (9.57:1) and Mirza Asif B [10] (4.70:1) who reported more of benign tumours in their studies.

However our study was comparable to study done by Kransdorf [11,12] (1995) (1.50:1) where there were increased numbers of malignant tumors, because of the difficult cases being referred to the specialty Centre.

Our institute is the largest referral Centre in the state so larger number of malignant cases are being referred here. In the present study ratio of benign-malignant tumors is 2.80:1 but Enzinger and Weiss

(2001) [4] mentions benign-malignant ratio of 100:1.

This is due to the fact that many benign tumors such as lipoma and hemangioma do not undergo biopsy as compared to sarcoma, which come to medical attention quite early. In the present study, the average age of benign tumours was 36.41 and that of malignant tumours was 46.89, which is comparable with the study conducted by Geeta Dev *et al* [16].

Histopathological Typing Of Soft Tissue Tumors

Among total cases Adipocytic tumors were the most common category found with 41 cases (27.33%) followed by Vascular tumors 31 cases (20.66%) and Peripheral nerve sheath tumors 28 cases (18.66%). Fibrohistocytic tumors constituted 7.33% (11 cases) of total cases. There were 10 cases (8%) of smooth muscle tumors, 8

cases of skeletal muscle tumors (5.33%) (Table 3)

These observations were somewhat similar to the study conducted by Agravat *et al.* [19]. Lipoma formed the bulk of benign

adipocytic tumours constituting 31 (30.69%) (Table 3) of cases. Our findings are similar to findings by Agravat *et al.*, [19] Jain *et al* [18] and Kransdorf [11,12] who reported 29%, 47.29%, and 16.1% lipomas in their respective studies.

Table 9: Showing Comparative analysis of type and behavior of soft tissue tumors.

Type of tumor	Jain <i>et al</i> [18]		Mirza Asif B [10]		Present study (2019)	
	Benign	Malignant	Benign	Malignant	Benign	Intermediate /Malignant
Adipocytic tumors	175 (47.29%)	11 (2.97%)	52 (37.95%)	3 (3.64%)	31 (20.66%)	10 (6.66%)
Vascular	70 (18.91%)	04 (1.08%)	21 (15.32%)	5	29 (19.33%)	4 (2.66%)
Peripheral nerve sheath tumors	69 (18.64%)	04 (1.08%)	8 (5.83%)	1 (0.72%)	26 (17.33%)	2 (1.33%)
Fibroblastic	11 (2.97%)	0	18 (13.13%)	2 (1.45%)	4 (2.66%)	8 (5.33%)
Fibrohistocytic	07 (1.89%)	05 (1.35%)	9 (6.56%)	5 (3.64%)	6 (4%)	5 (3.33%)
Smooth muscle tumors	02 (0.54%)	04 (1.08%)	3 (2.18%)		4 (2.66%)	6 (4%)
Skeletal muscle tumors	0	05 (1.35%)	-		1 (0.66%)	7 (4.66%)
Others	01 (0.27%)	02 (0.54%)	2 (1.45%)	8 (5.83%)	-	7 (4.66%)
Total	335 (90.54%)	35 (9.45%)	113 (82.48%)	24 (17.52%)	101 (67.33%)	49 (33%)

Lipomatous tumors: In our study, adipocytic tumors were the most common constituting 27.33% of cases (Table 3). These observations were somewhat similar to the study conducted by Agravat *et al* [19]. Lipoma formed the bulk of benign adipocytic tumors constituting 20.66% of cases (Table 3). Our findings are similar to findings by Agravat *et al* [19] and Kransdorf [11,12] who reported 29% and 16.1% lipomas in their respective studies. There were 8 cases of liposarcomas accounting for 22.22% of all malignant soft tissue tumors, with an average age of 52.28 years, age range of 31 years to 70 years of age (Table 3) and retroperitoneum being the common anatomical location (Table 4, Fig Ea, Eb). These findings are in correlation with the studies conducted by

Geeta Dev [17] *et al* and Kransdorf *et al* [11].

When graded according to FNCLCC grading system, Grade 1 liposarcomas were more than Grade 2 and 3 (Table 5) There were 3 cases of Grade 2 liposarcoma and grade 3 liposarcoma. Coindre *et al* [7] and Ducimetière *et al.* found Grade 1 liposarcomas to be the more common than Grade 2 tumors.

Vascular tumors: Hemangiomas were second most common among benign tumors constituting 27 (26.73%) cases. Out of 27 cases of hemangiomas, 6 cases were of lymph vessel origin. There were 2 cases of hemangioendothelioma and angiosarcoma (Table 3). Majority of hemangiomas occurred on head and neck (17 cases) (Table 6). These findings are in

good correlation with the studies reported by Geeta Dev *et al* [17], Agravat [19] and Kransdorf [11].

Table 10: Comparative analysis of incidence, age, sex and site distribution of vascular tumors

Authors	Type of tumor	No. of cases (% of benign/ Malignant tumors)	Mean age in years (range)	Sex (M:F)	Common site
Geeta Dev(1974) <i>et al</i> [17]	Benign	139(21.3)	8.7(<1-65)	2.1:1	Head and Neck
	Malignant	9(7.1%)			17-60
Kransdorf (1995) [11]	Benign	1418(7.6%)	28.8(<1-65)	1:1	Head and Neck
	Malignant	512(4.1%)			51(17-84)
Mirza [10](2005)	Benign	20(17.69%)	31.16(10-80)	0.8:1	Head and Neck
	Malignant	2(8.33%)			46(35-57)
Present Study(2019)	Benign	27(26.73%)	32.07(5-65)	1.25:1	Head and Neck
	Malignant	2(5.55%)			43(35-57)

In the present study 28 cases (18.66%) were of nerve tissue origin 26 (25.74%) were of benign origin and 2 were malignant (5.5%). (Malignant Nerve sheath tumor) (Table 3) which had 10 cases of neurofibroma, 8 of schwannoma and 1 of MPNST. 10 cases were from extremities, 4 from head & neck, 3 from back and 3 were from other sites. Majority of cases in our study were from extremities (19 cases)67%.

Fibrohistiocytic tumors:

Out of 11cases of Fibrohistiocytic tumors. ,6 were benign among which 3 cases of DFSP were found and 2 cases of Undifferentiated pleomorphic sarcoma (Table 3,4,6). On FNLCC grading Pleomorphic sarcoma was graded as Grade3(Table 5). IHC played a limited diagnostic role in Undifferentiated pleomorphic sarcoma which was a

diagnosis of exclusion(Table 9). Most common site was extremities(6 cases) while for DFSP trunk was most common site (2 cases)(Table 4).

Study of Agravat [19] et al had 5 cases of fibrohistiocytic tumors all of which were benign fibrohistiocytoma with age range of 10 days to 53 years and of them 3 cases were located on upper extremities.

Fibroblastic Tumors: Of 13 cases in the intermediate group Fibroblastic tumors constituted 46.15% (6 cases) of total cases.4 were in the benign group 6 were in the intermediate category and 2 in the Malignant category. (Table 3)

2 cases of elastofibroma one found on back and another on lower extremity were seen. (Table 6)

Smooth Muscle Tumors:

Of 10 cases of smooth muscle tumors, 4 (3.96%) were benign and 6 (16.66%) (Table 3) were malignant. All benign cases were angio leiomyoma found in extremities and back (Table 6). Leiomyosarcoma constituted 16.66% of total malignant tumors and were the third most common malignant STTs (Table 3). Among malignant tumors 4 were well differentiated leiomyosarcoma with FNCLCC grading predominantly 2 and 2 were Pleomorphic leiomyosarcoma with Grade 3. (Table 7)

3 cases of leiomyosarcoma were seen in extremities, 2 in retroperitoneum and 1 on trunk. (Table 4). Study of Hena Paul Singh [20] had leiomyosarcoma as second most common malignant soft tissue tumor.

Skeletal Muscle Tumors

Rhabdomyosarcoma were the second most common of all malignant soft tissue tumors constituting 19.44% of malignant soft tissue tumors and 4.66% of total soft tissue tumors. (Table 3) 4 cases of embryonal rhabdomyosarcoma were found in the head and neck region 1 was found on trunk (Table 6). Majority of Rhabdomyosarcoma were grade 1 with FNCLCC grading (4 cases). 2 cases were grade 3 and 1 case was grade 2 (Table 5). The results of our study were comparable with study of Hena Paul *et al* [20].

Tumors of Uncertain Differentiation.

They included ~ 4. % of total soft tissue tumors. There were 5 cases of synovial sarcoma including 1 case of monophasic sarcoma (Table 3). Majority of cases (4) were grade 2 (FNCLCC).. Most common site was lower extremities (Table 4)

1 case of extraskeletal Ewings/PNET was seen in 35 years female in shoulder region and another one in 10 yr old in lower extremity. The study of Hena Paul [20] had 12 cases (4.42%) of Tumors of uncertain differentiation.

Malignant category ($n = 9$) included synovial sarcoma ($n = 5$), primitive neuro ectodermal tumor [PNET ($n = 2$)], and desmoplastic round cell tumor ($n = 3$). On FNCLCC grading, maximum cases belonged to Grade 2 ($n = 4$) followed by Grade 3.

Role of immunohistochemistry

Since there is a marked overlap in morphological features of certain soft tissue tumors, role of IHC becomes instrumental in such cases for exact categorization. In the present study IHC was mostly used in malignant soft tissue tumors and occasionally in benign and intermediate tumors where morphology wasn't sufficient. It helped in making a definitive diagnosis in 7/13 intermediate, and 33/36 malignant STTs. IHC is also decisive in diagnosing some forms of other sarcomas, such as synovial sarcomas and malignant vascular tumors. (Table 9)

Thus, STTs include a large family of tumors with very few studies conducted on the whole spectrum and grading like FNCLCC. Our study highlights the importance of affected age group, sexual predilection, location, size, histopathology, and IHC features in diagnosing STTs.

STTs located superficially in young males were more likely benign, while larger tumors located deep in lower extremity or abdomen and retroperitoneum or mediastinum of older patients would be having high or intermediate malignant potential. However, RMS, PNET, and LGMS showed predilection for younger population and involved the head and neck.

Males were affected more than females though aggressive angiomyxoma and DFSP were seen more in females. FNCLCC grading helped in prognostication of malignant STTs and IHC helped in diagnosing cases which shared histopathological features with other sarcomas and carcinomas. Some tumors which were initially diagnosed as NOS were reclassified as LMS, RMS, and

synovial sarcoma after IHC. However, tumors of uncertain differentiation were even difficult to categorize using IHC. Hence, a good histopathological expertise with a panel of large number of IHC markers and cytogenetic and molecular studies may be needed to accurately diagnose these tumors.

Conclusion

STTs include a large family of tumors with very few studies conducted on the whole spectrum and grading like FNCLCC.

Our study highlights the importance of affected age group, sexual predilection, location, size, histopathology, and IHC features in diagnosing STTs. STTs located superficially in young males were more likely benign, while larger tumors located deep in lower extremity or abdomen and retroperitoneum or mediastinum of older patients would be having high or intermediate malignant potential. However, RMS, PNET, and LGMS showed predilection for younger population and involved the head and neck. Males were affected more than females though aggressive angiomyxoma and DFSP were seen more in females.

FNCLCC grading helped in prognostication of malignant STTs and IHC helped in diagnosing cases which shared histopathological features with other sarcomas and carcinomas. Some tumors which were initially diagnosed as NOS were reclassified as LMS, MFH, and synovial sarcoma after IHC. However, tumors of uncertain differentiation were even difficult to categorize using IHC. Hence, a good histopathological expertise with a panel of large number of IHC markers and cytogenetic and molecular studies may be needed to accurately diagnose these tumors

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